

DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH SKILLS IN ENGLISH LESSONS
AT GENERAL EDUCATIONAL SCHOOL

Makhmudova Zulhumor Rahmatullayevna

Andijon mashinasozlik instituti akademik

litseyi ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

Abstract: The article describes the methods of activating oral speech, describes effective means of forming oral and speech skills, and in particular, speaking skills of pupils. A set of interesting techniques aimed at the formation of oral speech skills of general educational school pupils in English lessons is given.

Keywords: oral speech, communicative competence, interactive methods, pedagogical technologies, roleplaying game, creative activity.

The problem of the development of oral speech of pupils at the senior stage of general educational school is becoming increasingly important since speech as the purpose of learning acts as a means of communication. Today, the aim of a modern school is to form a multicultural personality of pupils, which implies that they acquire a certain amount of knowledge about a foreign language, the formation of the ability not only to understand but also to communicate freely in it. As noted by O. A. Biryukova and D. V. Semenova, "the formation of the ability to produce one's own oral speech in monologue and dialogical forms in modern methodological science is postulated as the main goal of teaching a foreign language and is expressed through the concept of foreign language communicative competence, which, as is known, has a rather complex multicomponent structure". Oral speech as a productive process requires a lot of time and effort from the student since it also requires the inclusion of language, speech and communicative competencies. As a type of communicative activity, it should be an integral part of

every lesson. The main purpose of teaching a foreign language to pupils is the possession of basic speech structures that correspond to the threshold level of proficiency based on the All-European Scale of Language Competence. Teaching speaking is based on themes that meet the real needs and interests of pupils at the senior stage of general educational school. In order to facilitate the communication of pupils, it must be taken into account the specific features of this type of speech activity, such as motivation, purposefulness, activity, connection with the personality and mental activity of a person, heuristics, independence, pace and situativeness. If there are goals and motives for communication, the characteristic features of the communication participants, their age, level of development are taken into account, then the act of communication within the framework of any speech situation will certainly take place. Many English teachers face the problem of "silence of students" in the lessons of the development of conversational skills. In order to prevent this, modern pedagogical technologies suggest changing the educational situation in such a way that the teacher from "indisputable authority" becomes an attentive and interested interlocutor and accomplice in the process of cognition. The communicative method, as one of the modern methods of teaching English, helps to ensure that the teacher is not only a carrier of information but also an observer and consultant. The task of the teacher is to create situations of educational bilingualism that would facilitate the communication of pupils. The best methods of activating the oral speech of pupils are the techniques of human-to-human interaction, i.e. interactive techniques. Many scientists have contributed to the study of interactive teaching methods: L. N. Vavilova, G. D. Brown, T. N. Dobrynina, E. Ya. Golant, O. A. Golubkova, L. K. Geikhman, V. V. Guzeev, E. S. Zair-Bek, M.V. Clarin, E. E. Lushnikova, V. V. Nikolina, T. S. Panina, G. S. Kharkhanova, A. Yu. Prilepo and others. According to S. B. Suvorova, "interactive learning is a way of cognition, it is carried out only under the condition of joint activity of students. Interactive learning is based on the interaction of students and

the learning environment, which is an area of experience, based on the psychology of human relationships and interactions. Such training is considered as a joint process of cognition, in which knowledge is obtained in the process of joint activity through dialogue, polylogue" It follows from this that these methods involve the interaction of the subjects of the educational process at the level of "peerto-peer", where the teacher and the class participant are part of the same team, they work to achieve the same goal. It should be noted that teaching interactive interaction requires the use of educational material taken from life in English lessons, which, in properly organized conditions, promotes natural communication in the language being studied. In order to create situations of interactive interaction, it is necessary to exclude the restriction of work by tasks in which students need to imagine themselves in any situation. On the contrary, tasks are expedient, the very wording of which contains the need for interactive interaction. Such tasks are constructed in such a way that they cannot be done independently. S. B. Suvorova offers her own classification of interactive teaching methods based on communicative functions. In this classification, all methods are divided into three groups: 1) discussion (dialogue, group discussion, analysis and analysis of life situations); 2) gaming (didactic games, business games, roleplaying games, organizational and activity methods); 3) psychological group of interactive methods (sensitive and communicative training, empathy). It should be noted that interactive methods of teaching English can be widely used in high school when studying regional and social topics. As interactive approaches, we will highlight interactive lectures, roleplaying, imitation, educational games, which include, for example, "A student in the role of a teacher", "Everyone knows everyone", "Interviews", etc. The active mental activity of students is caused by tasks such as "A dozen questions", "Choice", during which students need to demonstrate their own perception of the surrounding world. Creative tasks under the names "Associations", "Choice of aphorism" are distinguished by their communicative

nature. The tasks "Reflexive circle", "Chain of wishes" are based on the methods of organizing reflexive activity and are aimed at developing the skills of introspection. Interactive methods also include discussions, business games, brainstorming, training, case method, classes in a playful way, etc. Specific situations close to the real ones are simulated in front of the students. Students need to solve a certain task, which leads to active involvement in the process of learning English. Further, it should be noted that one of the most popular forms of interactive classes is a role-playing game, that is, a game based on students performing certain role-playing functions and actions that involve making a decision. Role-playing involves participants imitating behavior corresponding to the role they have received. Properly organized role-playing is an effective means of developing decision-making skills. The actual game is based on the case method, which is a study and analysis of real situations with the subsequent proposal of possible solutions to a problem situation. One of the most effective forms of stimulating the creative activity of students is brainstorming, the essence of which is that before working with students, the teacher forms a problem, asks students a number of questions in order to get answers. During the lesson, students think about possible solutions to this problem. At the end of the lesson, the teacher and students summarize the results and mark the most creative ideas. It should be noted that games allow you to go beyond the traditional lesson both in a foreign language and in other subjects. This form of organization of the educational process expands the possibilities of both teachers and students, and encourages them to communicate, to dialogue in English in their group, gives each student the opportunity to get acquainted with the realities of foreign language communication without leaving the walls of the school. Role-playing games in comparison with traditional forms of English lessons in secondary school have the following advantages: 1) in a role-playing game, you can achieve a higher level of communication than in the process of traditional learning, since role-playing

involves performing specific actions, such as discussing a project, participating in a conference, communicating with colleagues; 2) role-playing is a collective activity that involves the active participation of the whole group as a whole and each of its members individually; 3) performing various tasks leads to a certain result, as a result of which students have a sense of satisfaction from joint actions and a desire to set and solve new tasks . The use of role-playing games in the process of teaching English in high school is possible only through modeling natural communication in a foreign language, in the process of which the principle of educative learning is implemented. The success of the role-playing game depends on clear modeling of the content plan and the expression plan. At the preparatory stage, students need to master the skills of linguistic design of communicative intentions, which will be needed to realize the goal of communication. In the process of direct preparation of the role-playing game, the teacher is engaged in processing the material that he receives from students, determines the type of game, the composition of participants, the goals of each participant of the project, plans possible ways to achieve goals, predicts problematic situations that may appear when solving tasks. Thus, in the process of teaching English to high school students, the use of interactive methods is very important, because it ensures the formation of communicative competence. In addition to knowledge of English, students have the opportunity to develop their personality, to form the skills necessary for future professional work, and for everyday life to communicate with other people

References

1. Biryukova, O. A. Teaching speaking in high school: interview method at the English language lesson / O. A. Biryukova, D. V. Semenova // Scientific Review. International Scientific and Practical Journal. - 2017.

2. Starodubtseva, O. G. Types of exercises for the formation of lexical skills of oral speech in a non-linguistic university [Text] / O. G. Starodubtseva // Scientific and Pedagogical Review. - 2013. - Issue 2 (2).
3. Konyshcheva A.V. Modern methods of teaching English. - Minsk: TetraSystems, 2011. - 304 p.
4. Suvorova N. A. Interactive learning: new approaches. M.: Verbum, 2005.

